

success story

> Pilot 4: Sustainable Urban Development Local | Regional Scale

The first solar cadastre of Athens: Technological innovation and real-life scenarios

The National Observatory of Athens, with support from the Eiffel project introduces the first "solar cadastre" for the city of Athens. The term refers to the geometric description and illustration of the solar energy potential that can be exploited by the respective urban building block with the use of rooftop photovoltaic systems. This service is an operational information platform aiming to support the penetration of solar systems into the urban fabric, while it will contribute to the decision making regarding the energy transition by offering environmentally friendly solutions.

The technology developed is based on the use of ultra-high-resolution Earth Observation data, advanced graphic creation platforms for three-dimensional ray tracing, radiative transfer models and supercomputer cloud architectures. It operates both climatically and in real-time, with the ultimate goal of facilitating urban planning, supporting the electricity distribution system operators of the produced energy and its efficient integration in the smart grids. The total rooftop usable area is able to massively host dispersed photovoltaics that can produce up to 4.3 terawatt hours (TWh) of energy per year, which in a hypothetical scenario of full rooftop coverage of buildings, can cover up to 49% of the total energy demand of Athens. For more information, follow the link: <http://solea.gr/athens-solar-cadastre/>

Useful links:

www.eiffel4climate.eu

<https://www.eiffel4climate.eu/index.php/pilots>

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